

PLOT OF SOBIR SAYQALI'S EPIC POEMS

Jumanov B.K.

Doctoral Student, Samarkand State University named after Sharof Rashidov

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Abstract. This article examines the plot of Sobir Sayqali's poem "Bakhrom and Gulandom," as well as its various versions. Sobir Sayqali was an Uzbek poet who lived and created in the 18th century. The article provides insights into the structure and storyline of the poem.

Keywords: Uzbek literature, Sobir Sayqali's poetry, divans, aruz, masnavi, classical literature, genre, imagery, "Bakhrom and Gulandom," epic, plot, Bakhrom Gor, heroic adventures, Ferdowsi, Nizami, Khusraw Dehlavi, Navoi.

Sobir Sayqali is a talented poet in the history of Uzbek literature. Sobir Sayqali is a prominent and talented poet who left a significant mark on the history of Hisor Uzbek literature. His seven masterpieces—*Qissai Ibrokhim Mukhammad*, *Qissai Shakhzoda Bakhrom va Malikai Gulandom*, *Qissai Khamro va Khurliqo*, *Ravzatush Shukhado*, *Akhtamnoma*, *Vaysul Qaran*, and *Zaynul Arab*—are testament to his literary prowess.

According to researchers, Sayqali lived in the second half of the 18th century. His life was marked by both material and spiritual hardships, which he lamented in his poetry, describing his time as oppressive and filled with sorrow:

*I am a broken soul, scorched by sorrow,
Oppressed and burdened by life's trials.
Fate's decree has ensnared me,
A lonely soul under the heavens' cruel blow...
A dark fate, an unfortunate destiny,
Trapped in a pit of suffering.
Grief is my steed, hardship my garment,
Wherever I go, toil is my companion...*

Research and Analysis of "Bakhrom and Gulandom"

Rakhim Aliyev has conducted research on *Bakhrom and Gulandom* and prepared the poem for publication. While this effort is commendable, it does not fully reveal all aspects of Sayqali's work. Much about the poet's life and his numerous other epics remains unexplored by literary scholars. Additionally, *Bakhrom and Gulandom* itself has not undergone comprehensive analysis.

The focus of this study is to examine the plot of Sayqali's epic, its connections and differences with other works of the same title, and the poet's mastery in crafting the narrative. Sayqali's influence on later epics of a similar nature underscores the importance of studying his unique style. To achieve this, we have referred not only to Aliyev's published version but also to the original manuscripts, as the prose version contains numerous omissions and stylistic inaccuracies. Notably, an entire chapter detailing Bakhrom's rescue of Rukhafzo, along with other significant passages, is missing. Additionally, many chapter titles have been copied incorrectly.

According to Sayqali's own testimony, *Bakhrom and Gulandom* was completed in the year 1201 Hijri (1786 CE). The poet states that he based his work on an older epic (*Dostoni Kokhan*) and reimagined it with a fresh approach:

*I crafted it according to my own style,
Reviving the ancient tale with a new design.*

What is this “epic”, in what language was it written, and who created it? Sayqali does not provide this information. We can only answer these questions by analyzing the events depicted in his work.

Upon examining Sayqali’s *Qissai Shakhzoda Bakhrom va Malikai Gulandom*, it becomes clear that the “ancient epic” he refers to is the **Persian-Tajik narrative** *Qissai Shakhzoda Bakhrom va Malikai Gulandom*. This narrative is primarily in **prose**, with occasional poetic verses. It was widely popular and printed several times through lithography in Iran, India, Pakistan, and Central Asia in subsequent centuries.

Sayqali’s Adaptation

Sayqali’s poem closely follows the **episodes, plot development, details, themes, and conclusions** of this prose narrative. The **names of the characters, settings, and structure** of the story remain unchanged. In some cases, Sayqali’s verses are almost identical in meaning to the original prose.

Original Prose:

“In the land of Rum, there was a wise and just king, possessing immense wealth and countless treasures...”

Sayqali’s Version:

*There was a king in the land of Rum,
Wise, eloquent, and just.
His wealth and treasures were vast,
Hidden away from the world.*

Original Prose:

“O son, the essence of kingship is to care for the people and eradicate the foundation of tyranny...”

Sayqali’s Version:

*Be a just and compassionate ruler,
A true leader of the people.
Understand the poor and uplift the oppressed,
Show mercy to orphans and follow righteous deeds.
Let generosity be your principle,
Always choose the path of goodness.
Act wisely and thoughtfully,
For these are always essential.*

The following poetic lines in Persian and Sayqali’s adaptation share remarkable similarities, even extending to specific expressions,

Persian Text:

*“Oh, sun of the royal constellation,
Your soul is a collection of divine grace.
I am amazed by your moon-like face,
My heart bewildered by your dark curls.
From longing, my heart is full of pain,
My lips are dry, my brow pale.”*

Sayqali's Version:

*"Oh, sun of the royal constellation,
Your face is a collection of divine grace.
I stand astonished by your moon-like visage,
My heart entangled in your dark curls.
Separation from you brings me endless pain,
My lips parched, my face pale."*

Despite these similarities, Sayqali's work exhibits many distinct characteristics. He has reinterpreted the Persian narrative in a fresh way, as he himself acknowledged, revitalizing the old epic ("I purified it"). While the storyline, composition, and events of the poem closely resemble the Persian *Qissai Shakhzoda Bakhrom va Malikai Gulandom*, as X.G. Korogli noted, it is not identical in all episodes and details. The inclusion of a poetic introduction (praise and eulogy), addressing the cupbearer, the use of ghazals and muhammas (types of Arabic verse), new metaphors, and concise titles, all add nuances that would fail to do justice to the poet's creativity if reduced to mere comparison.

Firstly, it must be noted that Sobir Sayqali has created a large and complete poetic epic from a small prose narrative. His work surpasses the Persian prose version by tenfold in terms of artistic and aesthetic value. The poet imbues the story with his own emotions, and his views on love and passion are skillfully embedded within the symbols, ensuring their perfection. The characters in Sayqali's version are much more vivid, logical, spiritually rich, and dynamic. Sayqali has refined the language of the work, beautifying it and reworking the plot into a written literary form. Although *Qissai Shahzoda Bakhrom va Gulandom* could be classified among the popular books, Sayqali's version stands at the crossroads of written literature and folklore, acting as a bridge that demonstrates the connection between them.

Moreover, it is important to point out that Sayqali's narrative is not exactly the same as the original prose version. In Sayqali's poem, the plot becomes significantly more complex, with events intricately interconnected and logically grounded. A prime example of this is the exchange of letters between Bakhrom and Gulandom, which, in the prose version, involves Bakhrom lying in the palace courtyard, making a lament, and then waiting for the princess's face-revealing ritual. Sayqali's version takes this interaction further, enhancing the depth of the characters and the emotional engagement of the plot.

In the prose version, Bakhrom, disguised in rags, lies in the courtyard of Gulandom's palace, lamenting, after which the princess's face-revealing ritual is described. Then, Bakhrom lifts the window's shutter at night to gaze at the girl's beauty. On the day of the Navruz festival, when Davlat gathers people for the celebration, the prince accidentally drops his ring. Upon seeing the ring, Gulandom realizes Bakhrom is the king's son. Later, when Gulandom comes out for the second face-revealing ritual, she looks at him with particular attention and smiles, and after returning to the pavilion, she sends Davlat to meet Bakhrom. In Sayqali's epic, however, there is no second face-revealing ritual. Instead, another event is depicted. Upon seeing the ring, Gulandom realizes that the young man is in love. She then leaves her throne, approaches the window, and looks at Bakhrom.

From the throne, Gulandom watched silently,
Through the window, Bakhrom gazed at her intently.
Their eyes met, and hearts were entwined,

In that moment, their souls were aligned.
Gulandom, captivated by Bakhrom's grace,
Became a servant to his beauty, in her place.
She showed herself to him in a moment's time,
Revealing her heart, in a way so sublime.
But soon, Gulandom, feeling ashamed of her act,
Returned to her throne, and the girls in her pack
Were scolded and driven from the house with might,
And secret tears fell from her eyes that night.
The girl who loved the prince, in sorrow did say:
"If only I could see him every day,
If I could behold his face each hour,
It would never be enough, his beauty would empower."
After this, she summoned Davlat, and commanded:
"Go, find this nameless youth, and demand it:
Who is he, where is he from, and where does he dwell?
Go, and uncover his story, his tale to tell".
The princess, who had suffered so much pain,
Wondered aloud, "Where has he come from in vain?
Who has endured such sorrow and strife,
To end up here, in this part of life?"

The poem begins with the couplet above, and Gulandom sends the first letter. Most of the subsequent letters (2-8) are close in meaning to the Persian version. In these, Bakhrom expresses his unsettled love through lamentation, while Gulandom "tests" him, responding with a flirtatious rejection. She insults him, saying that he is low, a servant, and not her equal. Davlat delivers their letters back and forth. In Sayqali's version, each letter is accompanied by a ghazal that adds additional layers to the emotional expression. However, the final letters (9, 10, 11) are significantly altered, with clearer depictions of the events.

In the Persian version, several letters inquire about Bakhrom's identity. In one of the last letters, when Bakhrom declares his princely lineage, Gulandom, touched by his words, advises patience, and the correspondence concludes with a shift to events unfolding in the city of Rum. In Sayqali's rendition, in the 9th letter, Gulandom firmly demands that Bakhrom reveal his identity, warning him that if he does not, the correspondence will end:

"Who is your father, where are you from, enough,
You speak these words without hesitation!
If you are a dervish, be a true dervish,
Make yourself equal to your peers!
If you are Bakhrom, reveal yourself,
For your words bring no benefit without that.
When you send this letter again,
Say your name, say your name, say your name!
If you don't say your name, don't send the letter,
Poor Davlat has grown weary in between".

In this part of the text, Bakhrom does not reveal his name, but he does confess that he is the son of a king. In the last part of the letter, he invites Gulandom for a walk in the garden, suggesting a meeting. Gulandom, relieved, writes her final letter, in which she advises patience and refrains from making her love public or lamenting excessively.

The interesting aspect here is that in the Persian version, Gulandom expresses that had Bakhrom not been a prince, she would not have agreed to his advances. After learning of his royal status, she accepts his proposal, and this sentiment is reflected in the final letter. In contrast, Sayqali, in his version, explains that Gulandom's repeated questioning of Bakhrom's identity stems from her previous openness about her love for him. She initially expressed her affection openly, which made it natural for her to seek clarification regarding his identity.

“My heart is inclined toward your love,
But there are many obstacles in between.
One could be if you were Bakhrom,
Or perhaps if you were a king in the end,
Then my father would accept you,
But there are obstacles, oh my beloved.
If I accept you, my father must consider you,
Otherwise, my father will reject you, and you must think of this”.

Gulandom indeed loves Bakhrom, but what truly matters to her is his royal status because her father's approval hinges on this. She knows that her father would not allow her to marry anyone who is not of royal blood, so she insists on Bakhrom revealing his identity as a prince to overcome these societal barriers and secure her father's consent. Once the final letter is delivered by Davlat, Bakhrom asks him to request a meeting between him and Gulandom, signaling the deepening of their connection despite the obstacles.

"If you don't come, let my sweet words be,
Let him come himself, and may my greetings reach him.
I will secretly reveal my consent to him,
If not, my soul will leave, without any regret".
Davlat also urges his queen to agree to this:
"O my flower, come, fulfill your promise to that young man,
With honor, place your promise at his feet".

Gulandom agrees and, using the excuse of going for a spring outing in the garden, leads her maidens out. Sayqali describes this episode with excitement and beautiful verses, as depicted in the post-independence period of Uzbek Navoiy studies. The maidens, while playing, pass by Bakhrom, and he recites a ghazal to them. The maidens go and tell Gulandom about this. Gulandom, using this as an excuse to see him, says, "Let me also have a look", and approaches Bakhrom. A playful exchange of questions and answers begins between them. This conversation takes the form of a *lapar* (a dialogue), where the content mentioned in the 10 letters is repeated. However, the poems' humorous tone and the use of a simple, fluent style, characteristic of the folk language, add a special charm to the narrative. Here are a few verses:

Gulandom says: "Oh, my condition on this journey, speak!
Oh, fate's torment, speak of my painful heartache!"
"What caused you to fall into this disgraceful state?
Now reveal your inner sorrow, tell me everything!"

The prince replies: "Listen to my important plea,
My condition is unbearable, hear my sorrowful sigh,
No one else has asked about my state,
Let me share my pain, slowly, with the king's daughter."
The prince continues: "You are my heavenly joy,
Your lips are sweeter than the red lips of the Kawsar.
If I die, I have no regrets, Oh, leader of beauties,
If my shoulder is your throne, my heart would bow in submission."
Gulandom replies: "Oh, you fool, lost in your own delusion,
This state of yours makes my heart no longer wish for you.
Each person should know their own condition and speak wisely,
It is better to bow your head under your own fate".

After the conversation, Gulandom, accompanied by her girls, goes back to the palace. Bakhrom, once again, is left alone, sighing in separation. After this, the poet shifts the focus to Bakhrom's father.

These episodes, introduced by Sayqali, significantly impact the plot and composition of the epic. Through these additions, the author ensures that the events follow a logical sequence, creating a natural connection between the episodes. This enhances the vitality and completeness of the characters, intensifying the authenticity of the depiction.

In the Persian version, Gulandom is depicted not as a lover lost in her beauty, but as a beloved who reciprocates Bakhrom's love with affection. In her portrayal, Bakhrom also becomes more refined. The Sayqali epic includes other additions that contribute to the artistic maturity and development of the plot. One could consider the Sayqali epic as a lyric-epic work, as it is full of lyrical moments. The poet brings to life the emotions of lovers, fathers and sons, friends, and brothers in a vivid and emotional manner. To achieve this, he makes effective use of classical poetic forms such as ghazals, mukhammas, and musaddas. Through these, he opens up the inner world of the characters, their heartbeat, and their emotions, giving them a voice.

Each ghazal and mukhammas is a unique and perfect work, and if they were all gathered into one collection, there is no doubt that it would become one of the most meaningful and beloved anthologies. Sayqali's poems, with their unique style and linguistic features, resemble the qualities of traditional Uzbek folk tales and the poetic style of powerful poets like Mashrab. In this way, his works harmonize with the tradition of folk poetry, joining the ocean of people's poetry with his own blood and soul.

Oh my dear, my cypress, my garden, my spring, you are my only one,
Oh my prince, my warrior, my pride in the eyes of the people, you are my only one,
Oh my dear, the joy of my wealth and state, you are my only one,
Oh king Rustam, my belief, my crown, you are my only one,
Without you, I have no peace, not a single moment of rest, you are my only one.
How could I live without you in this world of betrayal?
How could I live without you in this life, which is meaningless without you?
How could I live without you, the light of my soul, in this world of turmoil?
How could I live without you, my precious, in this world of fleeting moments?
I can no longer bear longing for you; there is no choice for me but to live in this world...

The poet was able to express the lament and sorrow of a father separated from his son in such a simple, flowing, and impactful way. One of the key characteristics that made Sobir Sayqali's epic famous among the people was this ability. This epic, with its remarkable qualities, influenced the literary life that followed.

Sayqali's ability to capture deep emotional states, like a father's grief, with such simplicity and power, made his work resonate strongly with the audience and left a lasting impact on subsequent literature.

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